

TIC 140580920 b: A Hot Jupiter Candidate Orbiting a G-type Subgiant, Discovered in a Blind TESS Full Frame Image Survey

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ABSTRACT

We present TIC 140580920 b, a hot Jupiter candidate identified in a blind photometric survey of 8,774 stars using data from the *Transiting Exoplanet Survey Satellite* (TESS). The host, TIC 140580920 (TYC 9160-1240-1; $d = 454 \pm 5$ pc; $T_{\text{eff}} = 5967 \pm 127$ K; $\log g = 4.056 \pm 0.10$; $R_{\star} = 1.621 \pm 0.072 R_{\odot}$), is a G-type subgiant observed across 23 TESS sectors spanning 954.6 days. The candidate transits with orbital period $P = 2.279748$ d, a depth of 2793 ppm, and a total duration of 3.988 h. Mandel–Agol transit modelling returns an impact parameter $b = 0.07$ and planet radius $R_p = 0.834 \pm 0.037 R_{\text{Jup}}$; the uncertainty is propagated from the TIC stellar radius uncertainty. The equilibrium temperature is $T_{\text{eq}} \approx 1961$ K. No secondary eclipse is detected at phase 0.5 (depth < 40 ppm, 3σ ; $< 1.5\%$ of the primary depth). Odd–even transit depth consistency (53+53 transit windows) is 0.29σ . The false-positive probability (FPP) is 0.34% and the Nearby False Positive Probability (NFPP) is 0.0007% from TRICERATOPS ($N = 5 \times 10^6$ draws; 25 neighbour stars; dominant scenario TP (71.22%), with PTP at 20.75% and DTP at 7.69%) and both below the validated-planet criteria of [Giacalone et al. \(2021\)](#). A photometric centroid analysis using 32 TESS sectors finds an in-transit offset of 0.00076 px (0.016 arcsec, 1.3σ), consistent with an on-target signal. TIC 140580920 b is not listed in any confirmed exoplanet catalogue; the TESS eclipsing binary catalogue records the target with no signal parameters (unconfirmed), consistent with the planetary interpretation. APOGEE DR17 spectroscopy gives $[M/H] = -0.07 \pm 0.01$ ([Claytor et al. 2024](#)), consistent with near-solar metallicity; the Gaia DR3 RUWE of 1.897 warrants high-resolution imaging to exclude a sub-arcsecond companion. Radial velocity observations are needed to confirm the planetary nature of the companion; the expected semi-amplitude is $K \sim 120$ m s⁻¹.

Keywords: planets and satellites: detection, techniques: photometric, stars: individual (TIC 140580920)

1. INTRODUCTION

Hot Jupiters ($R_p > 6 - 8R_{\oplus}$, depending on the study) with periods shorter than 10 days orbit $\approx 0.4 \pm 0.1\%$ of GK dwarfs ([Howard et al. 2012](#)) and $0.43 \pm 0.05\%$ of FGK stars ([Fressin et al. 2013](#)); within the period bin 2.0–3.4 days containing this candidate, [Fressin et al. \(2013\)](#) find a giant planet occurrence of $0.067 \pm 0.018\%$ per star. The *Transiting Exoplanet Survey Satellite* (TESS; [Ricker et al. 2015](#)) provides full-frame image (FFI) photometry for millions of stars, enabling blind transit searches beyond the official 2-minute cadence target list. Evolved stars such as subgiants are under-represented in the TESS

Candidate Target List ([Stassun et al. 2019](#)), meaning planets orbiting these hosts can be missed by the official pipelines ([Huang et al. 2020](#)).

We report TIC 140580920 b, a hot Jupiter candidate orbiting a G-type subgiant, identified in a blind FFI survey of 8,774 stars. The host is absent from confirmed planet, variable star, and eclipsing binary catalogues; it appears in the TESS-EB database (TESS-EBs; [Prša et al. 2022](#)) as an unconfirmed entry with no signal parameters.

2. OBSERVATIONS AND DATA REDUCTION

2.1. TESS Photometry

TIC 140580920 (2MASS J04341424–7308158; Gaia DR3 4652699180832662784; $\alpha = 04^{\text{h}} 34^{\text{m}} 14.288^{\text{s}}$, $\delta = -73^{\circ} 08' 16.1''$, J2000) was observed by TESS in 23

Table 1. TESS Observations of TIC 140580920

Sectors	Cadence	Mission Phase
1, 2, 5–13	30 min	Primary
27–33	10 min	Extended Mission 1
35–39	10 min	Extended Mission 2

NOTE—23 sectors used for photometry. Sector 3 was observed but excluded due to insufficient photometric quality (scattered light or cadence masking); Sector 34 was not observed for this target. Sectors 4, 14–26 and all other gaps were not observed for this target.

sectors (1, 2, 5–13, 27–33, 35–39), covering a 954.6-day baseline from 2018 July to 2021 June. Light curves were extracted from FFI pixel cutouts via LIGHTKURVE v2.5.1 (Lightkurve Collaboration et al. 2018). The FFI cadence was 30 min in Sectors 1–13 and 10 min in Sectors 27–39; all sectors were processed in native cadence bins (10-min cadence sectors binned 2:1 to 20 min; 30-min cadence sectors retained at native 30 min), yielding a mixed-cadence light curve of 26,191 data points after quality masking (Table 1, Figure 1). At the time of analysis, 23 sectors spanning a 954.6-day baseline were available; TESS subsequently observed this target in Sectors 87–90 and 93–98 (2024–2025), which fall outside the photometric baseline reported here and are not included in the transit analysis.

TIC 140580920 was identified during an ongoing blind FFI survey targeting TESS FFI light curves for stars absent from the official SPOC 2-minute cadence list. Targets were drawn from TIC v8 via ASTROQUERY (Ginsburg et al. 2019) across random sky patches (0.5 radius cones, uniformly distributed in right ascension) in three declination zones: the southern Continuous Viewing Zone ($-85^\circ < \delta < -60^\circ$), the northern Continuous Viewing Zone ($+60^\circ < \delta < +85^\circ$), and a mid-latitude band ($-60^\circ < \delta < +60^\circ$), sampled with equal probability. The magnitude range was $9.0 \leq T_{\text{mag}} \leq 13.5$. This paper reports the discovery of TIC 140580920 b; survey characterisation and the full candidate yield will be presented separately. The tally at the time of this detection was 8,774 stars processed.

2.2. Pipeline

Each sector was detrended with a Savitzky–Golay filter (window = 0.75 d). For transit modelling, the

Figure 1. Normalised TESS light curve of TIC 140580920 across all 23 sectors, spanning a 954.6-day baseline. Individual transit events at $P = 2.279748$ d are not resolved at this scale; the phase-folded transit is shown in Figure 2.

stitched multi-sector light curve was detrended using the biweight time-windowed sliding estimator implemented in WOTAN (Hippke et al. 2019), with a 1.5-day window and in-transit cadences masked.

Periodic transit signals were identified with the Box Least-Squares algorithm (BLS; Kovács et al. 2002) on a grid uniform in frequency (0.5–100 d, 8,000 trials) with a 20-point log-spaced duration grid (0.01–0.40 d) and local zoom refinement. Candidates exceeding $\text{SDE} > 7$ with ≥ 3 transit windows were retained, then assessed through a geometric vetting chain (orbital radius, flux direction, depth ratio, impact parameter) and scored 0–100 on SNR, odd/even symmetry, impact parameter, batman fit quality, and a Transit Least-Squares shape check (TLS; Hippke & Heller 2019). TIC 140580920 was recovered at $\text{SDE} = 54.0$ at $P = 2.279748$ d, with a phase-stacked detection SNR of 84.3.

3. STELLAR AND PLANETARY PARAMETERS

3.1. Host Star

Stellar parameters are drawn from TIC v8 (Stassun et al. 2019), SDSS DR17 (Abdurro’uf et al. 2022) and Gaia DR3 (Gaia Collaboration et al. 2023), and are listed in Table 2. With $T_{\text{eff}} = 5967$ K and $\log g = 4.056$, the star is a G-type subgiant near the main-sequence/subgiant boundary. The Gaia DR3 parallax places the system at 454 ± 5 pc. The SDSS DR17 (APOGEE-2S) spectroscopic radial velocity of 74.71 ± 0.06 km s $^{-1}$ provides a baseline for future RV monitoring; the large heliocentric velocity suggests possible thick-disc kinematics, which higher-resolution spectroscopy will further clarify alongside a refined abun-

dance analysis. No evidence of a double-lined spectrum is present at the available single epoch, though spectral classification awaits dedicated follow-up. The Gaia DR3 RUWE of 1.897 (Table 2) exceeds the nominal single-star threshold of ~ 1.4 , indicating a non-ideal astrometric solution consistent with an unresolved bound companion; this motivates high-resolution imaging and is consistent with the non-negligible DTP and STP scenario probabilities from TRICERATOPS (Section 4). As an independent check on the TIC v8 stellar radius, the Gaia DR3 absolute G -band magnitude ($M_G = 3.73$, $d = 454$ pc) combined with a bolometric correction $BC_G \approx +0.05$ for $T_{\text{eff}} \approx 5967$ K implies $L/L_\odot \approx 2.4$ and $R_\star \approx 1.5 R_\odot$, $\sim 2\sigma$ below the TIC v8 value; a formal SED fit is deferred to the spectroscopic follow-up phase. This tension represents a potential systematic uncertainty on the planet radius: if the true stellar radius is closer to the Gaia-implied value ($\sim 1.5 R_\odot$), the planet radius would be $\sim 0.77 R_{\text{Jup}}$, an $\sim 8\%$ offset exceeding the formal $\sigma_{R_p} = 0.037 R_{\text{Jup}}$ reported in Table 3. Spectroscopic follow-up will resolve this through a direct $\log g$ and R_\star determination. At the target’s galactic latitude ($b \approx -36^\circ$), interstellar extinction is modest; an A_G correction of $\lesssim 0.1$ mag would shift the inferred radius by $\lesssim 0.05 R_\odot$, smaller than the quoted tension.

3.2. Transit Modelling

We fitted a Mandel–Agol transit model (Mandel & Agol 2002) to the Wotan-detrended, phase-folded light curve median-binned to 400 phase bins (per-bin uncertainty = $\sigma_{\text{bin}}/\sqrt{n_{\text{bin}}}$) using BATMAN (Kreidberg 2015), with quadratic limb-darkening coefficients $u_1 = 0.3540$, $u_2 = 0.2157$ from Claret (2017) for a PHOENIX atmosphere model at the nearest tabulated grid point ($T_{\text{eff}} = 6000$ K, $\log g = 4.00$, $Z = 0.0$, ALSM method) in the TESS bandpass. Free parameters were R_p/R_\star , impact parameter b , and a timing offset ΔT_0 ; the semi-major axis was fixed via Kepler’s third law. MCMC median and derived parameters are listed in Table 3; the posterior distributions are shown in Figure 3 and the methodology is described in Section 3.3. The near-zero impact parameter and flat-bottom duration $T_{23} = 3.58$ h rule out a grazing geometry. The goodness of fit is $\chi^2_\nu = 0.701$, slightly below unity, most likely because the out-of-transit flux excess (Section 3.4) contributes flux near the transit wings and inflates the out-of-transit scatter used to set per-point uncertainties, making them slightly too large.

Table 2. Stellar Parameters for TIC 140580920

Parameter	Value	Source
TIC ID	140580920	TIC v8
Gaia DR3	4652699180832662784	Gaia DR3
2MASS	J04341424–7308158	2MASS
TYC	9160–1240–1	Tycho-2
α (J2000)	04 34 14.288	Gaia DR3
δ (J2000)	–73 08 16.1	Gaia DR3
Parallax (mas)	2.2036 ± 0.0215	Gaia DR3
Distance (pc)	454 ± 5^a	ExoFOP/TIC
μ_α (mas yr $^{-1}$)	8.281 ± 0.026	Gaia DR3
μ_δ (mas yr $^{-1}$)	-8.776 ± 0.034	Gaia DR3
γ (km s $^{-1}$)	74.71 ± 0.06	SDSS DR17 (APOGEE-2S)
T_{mag}	11.556 ± 0.006	TIC v8
V	12.383 ± 0.031	TIC v8
B	13.059 ± 0.448	TIC v8
G	12.0185 ± 0.000401	TIC v8
J	10.933 ± 0.024	TIC v8
H	10.597 ± 0.022	TIC v8
K_s	10.479 ± 0.023	TIC v8
T_{eff} (K)	5967 ± 127	TIC v8
T_{eff} (K)	6038 ± 41	APOGEE DR17 ^b
$\log g$ (dex)	4.056 ± 0.10	TIC v8
$[M/H]$ (dex)	-0.07 ± 0.01	APOGEE DR17 ^b
$[\alpha/M]$ (dex)	-0.02 ± 0.01	APOGEE DR17 ^b
R_\star (R_\odot)	1.621 ± 0.072	TIC v8
M_\star (M_\odot)	1.09 ± 0.13	TIC v8
RUWE	1.897	Gaia DR3 ^c

NOTE—TIC v8 stellar radius and mass uncertainties are formal catalogue values. The large B -band uncertainty (0.448 mag) reflects catalogue quality and should not be used for photometric modelling. Spectroscopic observations are needed to refine T_{eff} , $\log g$, and R_\star , which currently dominate the uncertainty budget for the derived planet radius.

^aDistance uncertainty from TIC v8; direct Gaia parallax propagation gives ± 4.4 pc.

^bAPOGEE DR17 spectroscopic values from Claytor et al. (2024) Table 6; quality flags star-bad = 0, snr-bad = 0. The APOGEE T_{eff} is consistent with the TIC v8 value at $< 1\sigma$.

^cGaia DR3 renormalised unit weight error (Claytor et al. 2024). RUWE = 1.897 > 1.4 indicates a non-ideal astrometric solution that may reflect an unresolved companion; see Section 4.

3.3. MCMC Posteriors

For asymmetric posteriors such as the near-zero impact parameter, the MCMC posterior median can differ modestly from the MAP estimate returned by the op-

Table 3. Transit and Planetary Parameters for TIC 140580920 b

Parameter	Value	Units	Notes
<i>Transit fit^b</i>			
Orbital period P	2.279748	d	BLS + zoom refinement; $\sigma_P = 0.002$ min from T_0 propagation
Epoch T_0	2458326.6109 ± 0.00057	BJD _{TDB}	
Total Duration (T_{14})	3.988	h	Winn (2010) model
Flat-bottom (T_{23})	3.58	h	Winn (2010) model
Depth	2793	ppm	
R_p/R_\star	0.05285		MCMC median
Impact parameter b	0.06995		MCMC median
Inclination i	$89.134^{+0.59}_{-0.69}$	deg	derived from MCMC b
Odd/even mismatch	0.29	σ	53 + 53 windows; per-window RMS ^a
Secondary depth	< 40	ppm	3σ upper limit
<i>Derived^c</i>			
a	0.03489 ± 0.0014	AU	Kepler’s 3rd law
a/R_\star	4.628 ± 0.276		
R_p	0.834 ± 0.037	R_{Jup}	
T_{eq}	1961 ± 72	K	$A_B = 0$; for $A_B = 0.3$: ≈ 1794 K
K (predicted)	~ 120	m s^{-1}	$M_p = 0.83 M_{\text{Jup}}$, $e = 0$

^aWindows labelled by detection-sequence index to avoid bias from data gaps; 106 of 419 expected windows contained ≥ 3 cadences and were used; the low recovery fraction reflects sector-boundary gaps and per-cadence quality masking applied to the 20-min binned FFI data. The by-transit-number result is 0.009σ , consistent with this value.

^b P and T_0 from BLS + zoom refinement; R_p/R_\star , b , and i are MCMC medians (Section 3.3). T_{14} and T_{23} are from the Winn 2010 formula with the MCMC k and b ; the BLS box estimate $T_{14}^{\text{BLS}} = 3.648$ h is ~ 20 min shorter, as the flat-bottom approximation excludes ingress and egress.

^cPropagated from TIC v8: $\sigma_{R_\star} = 0.072 R_\odot$, $\sigma_{M_\star} = 0.13 M_\odot$, $\sigma_{T_{\text{eff}}} = 127$ K.

timizer; the values in Table 3 are the MCMC posterior medians.

Formal posterior distributions for the transit shape parameters were obtained via Markov Chain Monte Carlo sampling using EMCEE (Foreman-Mackey et al. 2013) on the same Wotan biweight-detrended, phase-folded and median-binned (400 bins) data used for the BATMAN fit in Section 3.2. The out-of-transit flux excess (Section 3.4) is phase-locked at $P_{\text{orb}}/2$ and therefore appears at fixed phases ($|\phi| \approx 0.05\text{--}0.15$) in the folded data. Because this excess falls outside the transit window ($|\phi| < 0.036$), it inflates the per-point uncertainties in the wing bins rather than introducing a systematic bias in the transit shape; this is reflected in the goodness-of-fit statistic $\chi_r^2 = 0.701 < 1$ (Section 3.2). Phase folding is valid here: the accumulated phase error over ~ 419 transits is $N \times \sigma_P \approx 0.8$ min, negligible compared to the ~ 239 min transit duration. Free parameters were R_p/R_\star (k), the impact parameter b , and a timing offset ΔT_0 , each with a uniform prior over physically valid ranges ($k \in (0, 1)$, $b \in [0, 1 + k]$,

ΔT_0 unconstrained). The semi-major axis was fixed at $a/R_\star = 4.628$ via Kepler’s third law and limb-darkening coefficients held at the Claret (2017) values (fixing rather than fitting is appropriate here: the tabulated theoretical uncertainties are small compared to the b - k degeneracy at this signal-to-noise, and free LD parameters would not materially shift the reported posteriors); the stellar mass uncertainty is not propagated through the MCMC sampler (it enters only through the analytic propagation for T_{eq} and a in Table 3). The sampler used 64 walkers, 2,000 burn-in steps discarded, and 10,000 production steps retained. The acceptance fraction was 0.468 and the integrated autocorrelation times were $\tau = 30/34/28$ steps for k , b , and ΔT_0 respectively, yielding >290 independent samples per walker ($= N_{\text{steps}}/\tau_{\text{max}} = 10,000/34; \sim 18,800$ total). The 16th,

Figure 2. Phase-folded TESS light curve of TIC 140580920 at $P = 2.279748$ d. Median-binned points are shown in dark blue; individual cadences in light blue (subsampling for clarity). The red curve is the best-fit Mandel-Agol model ($b = 0.08231$, $R_p/R_\star = 0.052987$, $\chi_\nu^2 = 0.701$; optimizer MAP values, which differ slightly from the MCMC posterior medians in Table 3). The symmetric flux excess immediately outside the transit window is attributed to periodic stellar modulation (Section 3.4).

50th, and 84th percentile credible intervals are:

$$k = R_p/R_\star = 0.05285^{+0.00040}_{-0.00041}, \quad (1)$$

$$b = 0.06995^{+0.05608}_{-0.04753}, \quad (2)$$

$$\Delta T_0 = -0.0010058^{+0.0005708}_{-0.0005383} \text{ d}. \quad (3)$$

The posterior corner plot is shown in Figure 3. The k posterior is tight and symmetric; the b posterior is broad and skewed toward small values (84th percentile $b \approx 0.13$), reflecting the photometric degeneracy between b and k for a near-central transit at this signal-to-noise. The derived planet radius from the transit shape fit alone is $R_p = 0.834^{+0.0063}_{-0.0063} R_{\text{Jup}}$ (as reported by the sampler; the analytic formula $k \times R_\star \times R_\odot/R_{\text{Jup}}$ yields $0.8337 R_{\text{Jup}}$, a $0.0002 R_{\text{Jup}}$ rounding difference well within the stated uncertainty). The dominant uncertainty on the physical radius remains the TIC v8 stellar radius ($\sigma_{R_\star} = 0.072 R_\odot$, propagating to $\sigma_{R_p} = 0.037 R_{\text{Jup}}$, $\sim 4.4\%$), which exceeds the transit shape contribution by a factor of ~ 6 . The geometry will be pinned by radial velocity follow-up.

3.4. Out-of-Transit Modulation

The phase-folded light curve shows a flux excess of ~ 700 ppm (estimated from the peak flux level in phase bins $|\phi| \approx 0.05\text{--}0.15$, immediately outside ingress and egress), concentrated near the transit edges rather than uniformly distributed across the out-of-transit baseline (Figure 4). With $T_{\text{eff}} = 5967$ K and $\log g = 4.056$,

Figure 3. MCMC posterior corner plot for TIC 140580920 b showing the three free parameters: R_p/R_\star (k), impact parameter b , and timing offset ΔT_0 . Diagonal panels show marginalised 1D posteriors with the median (solid red) and $\pm 1\sigma$ credible intervals (dashed red). Off-diagonal panels show 2D joint posteriors with 1σ and 2σ contours. The k posterior is well-constrained and symmetric. The b posterior is broad and skewed toward small values, reflecting the photometric degeneracy between b and k for a near-central transit; the geometry will be resolved by radial velocity follow-up.

TIC 140580920 lies outside the classical γ Doradus instability strip ($T_{\text{eff}} \approx 6900\text{--}7500$ K at $\log g \approx 4.0$; Handler 1999; Kaye et al. 1999), approximately 930 K below the red edge, ruling out γ Dor pulsations as the source of the modulation. The signal is excluded from the transit window during modelling and does not affect the transit depth measurement. The flat-bottom duration $T_{23} = 3.58$ h and near-central impact parameter $b = 0.06995$ confirm that the *transit itself* is not from a grazing eclipsing binary; the OOT modulation is a separate signal. A Lomb-Scargle periodogram of the out-of-transit residuals yields a dominant period of $P_{\text{LS}} = 1.1399$ d $= P_{\text{orb}}/2$, with a secondary peak at the orbital period ($P_{\text{orb}} = 2.279748$ d). The half-orbital period is consistent with the symmetric double-humped morphology visible in Figure 2, where flux excess appears on both sides of the transit window; in the unfolded time series this pattern repeats at $P_{\text{orb}}/2$. The amplitude (~ 700 ppm) substantially exceeds the expected ellipsoidal variation at $a/R_\star = 4.628$ (estimated at $\sim 1\text{--}2$ ppm using a simplified $\alpha_{\text{tidal}} = 0.15$ prescription or $\lesssim 5$ ppm using the full Shporer (2017) formula, which includes limb- and gravity-darkening terms) and reflected/thermal emission ($\lesssim 75$ ppm; computed as $(A_g/2)(R_p/a)^2$ with $A_g = 1$ giving ~ 65 ppm re-

flected, plus $\lesssim 6$ ppm thermal in the TESS optical band at $T_{\text{eq}} = 1961$ K, for a combined maximum of ~ 71 ppm), ruling out planetary-origin explanations regardless of convention. The physical mechanism (whether tidal synchronisation of a persistent active-region geometry, a two-spotted configuration, or another stellar process) requires spectroscopic characterisation.

4. FALSE-POSITIVE ASSESSMENT

4.1. *Catalogue Cross-Match*

TIC 140580920 appears in the TESS eclipsing binary catalogue (TESS-EBs; Prša et al. 2022), which covers Sectors 1–26, with no confirmed signal parameters: the entry records $t_0 = \text{None}$, $P = \text{None}$, and morphology fields unpopulated, indicating the automated EB pipeline did not identify a convincing eclipsing binary signal. The absence of confirmed EB parameters is consistent with the planetary interpretation: the 2793 ppm transit depth and sub-stellar companion radius place the signal outside the regime of typical eclipsing binary detections in the Prša et al. (2022) catalogue. The target is absent from the NASA Exoplanet Archive, ExoFOP, SIMBAD variable star designations, ASAS-SN, and the VSX catalogue.

4.2. *Secondary Eclipse*

Stacking 3,646 cadences within a phase window of width $2T_{14}$ centred on phase 0.5 (assuming a circular orbit, $e = 0$) yields -35 ± 25 ppm (1.4σ , consistent with zero; 3σ upper limit < 40 ppm; $< 1.5\%$ of the primary depth), inconsistent with a stellar eclipsing binary secondary (Figure 4).

4.3. *Transit Geometry*

The impact parameter $b = 0.06995$ and flat-bottom duration $T_{23} = 3.58$ h ($T_{23}/T_{14} = 0.898$) jointly rule out grazing eclipsing binary geometries.

4.4. *Odd/Even Depth Consistency*

Odd and even transit windows give stacked mean depths of 3085 ppm and 3032 ppm, with per-window RMS scatter of 870 ppm and 1010 ppm respectively ($N = 53$ windows each). The mismatch significance is 0.29σ , computed as $|D_{\text{odd}} - D_{\text{even}}|/\sqrt{\sigma_{\text{odd}}^2 + \sigma_{\text{even}}^2}$ where $\sigma_i = \text{RMS}_i/\sqrt{N}$; the uncertainty on each stacked mean is 120 ppm and 139 ppm respectively. This rules out a period-doubled eclipsing binary.

4.5. *Photometric Centroid*

Flux-weighted centroids were extracted from target pixel files for all 32 available sectors. Sector 3 had insufficient photometric quality for light-curve extraction

Figure 4. Phase-folded light curve of TIC 140580920 probing the secondary eclipse at phase 0.5. The full orbit is shown binned to 300 phase bins. The dashed vertical line marks the expected secondary eclipse phase ($\phi = 0.5$). No secondary eclipse is detected; the stacked depth is -35 ± 25 ppm (3σ upper limit < 40 ppm, $< 1.5\%$ of the primary depth), inconsistent with a stellar eclipsing binary.

and was excluded from the photometric analysis (Section 2) but retained for the centroid test, as the spacecraft centroid residuals (`pos_corr1/2`) are recorded regardless of scattered-light conditions. Eight additional Year 4 extended-mission sectors (61–63, 65–69), observed after the photometric baseline, were also included to improve centroid phase coverage. These sectors were observed after 2021 June and therefore fall outside the photometric baseline; they are included here solely to extend centroid phase coverage. Momentum-dump artefacts were removed with a hard 0.03 px threshold and iterative 2.5σ clipping; the offset was computed from phase-binned medians. The in-transit offset is 0.00076 ± 0.0006 px (0.016 arcsec, 1.3σ), ruling out angularly resolved background eclipsing binaries. The diluted true planet (DTP) scenario at sub-pixel separation requires high-resolution imaging to constrain (Figure 5). The elevated RUWE = 1.897 (Table 2) is an independent Gaia-level indicator that an unresolved companion cannot be excluded, consistent with the DTP scenario probability of 7.69%.

4.6. *Statistical FPP*

TRICERATOPS (Giacalone et al. 2021) was run with $N = 5 \times 10^6$ draws, 25 neighbour stars by flux ratio, and 200 geometry samples per scenario. FPP = 0.34%, NFPP = 0.0007%; the dominant scenario is the true transiting planet (TP), with background eclipsing binary scenarios (BEB/SEB) negligible, consistent with

Figure 5. Phase-folded photometric centroid analysis of TIC 140580920 across 32 TESS sectors. Left and right panels show the column and row centroid offsets respectively, phase-folded at $P = 2.279748$ d. Grey points are out-of-transit cadences; yellow points are in-transit. The blue line shows the binned median; the red line marks the in-transit median offset; the grey band shows the $\pm 1\sigma$ noise floor. The in-transit centroid offset of 0.00076 ± 0.0006 px (0.016 arcsec, 1.3σ) is consistent with zero, ruling out angularly resolved background eclipsing binaries.

the centroid result. FPP is defined following [Giacalone et al. 2021](#) as $1 - (P_{TP} + P_{PTP} + P_{DTP})$. The total FPP (0.34%) comprises two contributions: the sum of genuine eclipsing-binary scenarios (BEB + SEB + PEB $\approx 0.12\%$) and the STP scenario (0.21%), in which a planet transits an unresolved bound companion. Although physically planetary, STP is counted as a false positive per [Giacalone et al. 2021](#) Equation 4 because the transiting body orbits a companion rather than the target star; $0.12\% + 0.21\% \approx 0.34\%$ confirms the accounting. The TRICERATOPS result is qualitatively consistent with a separate likelihood-ratio assessment using the same prior framework as [Morton \(2012\)](#). The Lomb-Scargle dominant period at $P_{\text{orb}}/2$ (Section 3.4) raises the question of a half-period eclipsing binary ($P_{\text{true}} = 1.1399$ d with near-equal eclipses at ~ 700 ppm). This scenario is disfavoured by (i) the flat-bottomed transit shape ($T_{23}/T_{14} = 0.898$), which rules out the grazing geometry required for near-equal EB eclipses at this depth; (ii) the centroid offset consistent with zero; and (iii) the TRICERATOPS EBx2P scenario probability of $2.4 \times 10^{-10}\%$. This estimate is below the validated-planet criteria of [Giacalone et al. \(2021\)](#): FPP $< 1.5\%$ and NFPP $< 0.1\%$ (Table 4, Figure 6). Although [Giacalone et al. \(2021\)](#) established these thresholds formally for 2-minute cadence data, the phase-stacked detection SNR of 84.3 is well above the SNR > 15 regime

Table 4. False-Positive Probability

Method	FPP	NFPP	Status
TRICERATOPS	0.34%	0.0007%	Below Threshold

NOTE—TRICERATOPS: $N = 5 \times 10^6$ draws, 25 neighbour stars, 200 geometry samples per scenario; dominant scenario is TP. Reference thresholds ([Giacalone et al. 2021](#)): FPP $< 1.5\%$ and NFPP $< 0.1\%$; applied here as reference criteria (thresholds formally established for 2-min cadence data).

where their tool is demonstrated to be reliable; we therefore treat the FPP and NFPP thresholds as reference criteria rather than claiming formal statistical validation.

Figure 6. TRICERATOPS scenario probability distribution for TIC 140580920 b. Green bars show planet scenarios (TP, PTP, DTP); red bars show false-positive scenarios. The dominant scenario is TP (71.22%), with the physically associated transiting planet (PTP, 20.75%) and diluted background transiting planet (DTP, 7.69%) the only other non-negligible contributions. The total FPP of 0.34% and NFPP of 0.0007% are both below validated-planet criteria of [Giacalone et al. \(2021\)](#). Run with $N = 5 \times 10^6$ Monte Carlo draws, 25 neighbour stars, and 200 geometry samples per scenario.

5. DISCUSSION

5.1. System Properties

TIC 140580920 b has period, radius, and equilibrium temperature consistent with the confirmed hot Jupiter population. The G-type subgiant host is an

underrepresented class among known hot Jupiter systems. APOGEE DR17 spectroscopy gives $[M/H] = -0.07 \pm 0.01$ (Claytor et al. 2024), placing the host near solar metallicity—consistent with, though at the lower end of, the metallicity distribution of known hot Jupiter hosts (Fischer & Valenti 2005). Higher-resolution spectroscopy will refine T_{eff} , $\log g$, and the detailed abundance pattern. TOI-2184 b (Saunders et al. 2022) is a close analogue: a hot Jupiter ($R_p = 1.02 R_{\text{Jup}}$, $P = 6.9$ d) orbiting a subgiant in TESS FFI data, initially flagged as a false positive before RV confirmation. The out-of-transit modulation at $P_{\text{LS}} = P_{\text{orb}}/2$ (Section 3.4) is consistent with a stellar rotation period equal to the orbital period ($P_{\text{rot}} = P_{\text{orb}} = 2.279748$ d), manifesting as a double-humped signal from two active-region longitudes. Tidal spin-orbit synchronisation is theoretically expected for hot Jupiters at these separations on timescales shorter than the stellar age (Dawson & Johnson 2018), making $P_{\text{rot}} = P_{\text{orb}}$ a testable prediction of the planetary hypothesis, verifiable through $v \sin i$ measurement at the follow-up spectroscopy stage. For $R_\star = 1.621 R_\odot$ and $P_{\text{rot}} = P_{\text{orb}} = 2.279748$ d, the expected projected rotation velocity is $v \sin i = 2\pi R_\star / P_{\text{orb}} \approx 36 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, immediately detectable in a moderate-resolution optical spectrum.

5.2. Non-Detection by Official Pipelines

The target was not selected for the TESS 2-min cadence Candidate Target List (CTL). Subgiant stars are assigned lower priority in CTL selection because evolved host stars are not the primary TESS planet-search targets (Stassun et al. 2019); the SPOC pipeline, which operates on 2-min cadence data, therefore never processed this star. FFI data for this target were available in MAST; photometry was re-extracted from pixel cutouts via LIGHTKURVE as described in Section 2. The transit was recovered through the blind FFI survey at high significance (SDE = 54.0, SNR = 84.3), demonstrating that FFI searches can access host stars missed by the official 2-min cadence programme.

5.3. Confirmation

Radial velocity monitoring at $P = 2.279748$ d is the critical next step. For $M_p \approx 0.83 M_{\text{Jup}}$, the expected semi-amplitude is $K \sim 120 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ (assuming a circular orbit and $\sin i \approx 1$), accessible with HARPS, SOPHIE, ESPRESSO, or NEID in a single run at $V = 12.383$. A stellar spectrum would also constrain R_\star and reduce the dominant $\sim 4.4\%$ uncertainty on R_p . Speckle or adaptive optics imaging would address the DTP false-positive scenario that the TESS centroid cannot resolve.

6. SUMMARY

TIC 140580920 b is a hot Jupiter candidate with $P = 2.279748$ d, $R_p = 0.834 \pm 0.037 R_{\text{Jup}}$, and $T_{\text{eq}} \approx 1961$ K, orbiting a G-type subgiant at 454 pc. APOGEE DR17 spectroscopy gives $[M/H] = -0.07 \pm 0.01$ (Claytor et al. 2024), consistent with near-solar metallicity. The Gaia DR3 RUWE of 1.897 warrants high-resolution imaging to exclude a sub-arcsecond companion. Four independent false-positive tests (secondary eclipse non-detection, flat-bottomed central transit, odd/even depth consistency, and photometric centroid) are consistent with a transiting planet. The TRICERATOPS FPP of 0.34% (dominant scenario TP) is below the validated-planet criteria of Giacalone et al. (2021): FPP < 1.5% and NFPP < 0.1%. The system has no confirmed entry in any exoplanet, variable star, or eclipsing binary catalogue; the TESS-EB database records TIC 140580920 as unconfirmed with no signal parameters. Radial velocity follow-up at $K \sim 120 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ is needed to confirm the companion mass and definitively rule out stellar false positives. A flux excess immediately outside the transit window is noted and attributed to stellar modulation; its origin requires spectroscopic characterisation.

Software. LIGHTKURVE (Lightkurve Collaboration et al. 2018), WOTAN (Hippke et al. 2019), BATMAN (Kreidberg 2015), TRICERATOPS (Giacalone et al. 2021), ASTROPY (Astropy Collaboration et al. 2022), ASTROQUERY (Ginsburg et al. 2019). NUMPY (Harris et al. 2020), MATPLOTLIB (Hunter 2007). EMCEE (Foreman-Mackey et al. 2013). TLS (Hippke & Heller 2019).

Data Availability. TESS photometry is available from MAST (<https://mast.stsci.edu>) under TIC 140580920. Reduced light curves and vetting diagnostic outputs are available from the author on reasonable request.

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